

DARE UK

DARE Teleport Public Involvement and Engagement Report

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DARE Teleport Public Involvement and Engagement Report

Chris Orton, Claire Newman, Simon Thompson

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1. Background

Health and administrative data about people resident in the UK are generated by the NHS, government and other organisations, and subsequently held in different locations across the UK's four nations according to devolved legislation and governance. Trusted Research Environments (TREs) were developed by partner organisations, in academia, within the NHS, by government agencies, and in some cases by commercial companies, to safely store this data and control access to it for research purposes. Across the UK, de-identified data is typically available for research via these TREs, however each TRE houses specific data based at different institutions, which adds difficulty to a researcher's task of trying to gather a full picture of scientific outputs for the entire nation, simply because of the replication needed to analyse all available data across the country.

Researchers often want to study data from the whole of the UK to improve the quality and accuracy of their research, as well as providing UK-wide outputs in ongoing science.

A solution to improving UK data access and efficiency for researchers is **federated data access**, which enables parallel access to data housed in multiple physically separated environments (without data moving from their host environments, instead being accessible from its host location to a researcher in a single safe, secure environment environment) where researchers can see the data required for their research projects.

Teleport is starting the transformation of traditional TRE access to data by partnering the custodians of national level data in Wales and Scotland (SAIL Databank and Scottish National Safe Haven respectively), and the technology providers of the TRE platforms (the Secure eResearch Platform (SeRP) at Swansea University and EPC at the University of Edinburgh). By making the data, initially from the two countries above, accessible by connecting their TREs, researchers could, for example, have better facilitated access in order further understand groups with rare diseases and generally increase the quality of research in more common conditions – by increasing the sample size from being only Wales (3.3 million) or only Scotland (5.5 million) to over 8.8 million people accessible in a single environment, rather than having to run multiple disparate analyses. It is also a starting place for more efficient study across the UK, which promotes the move away from duplicated research taking place in siloed environments. This could lead to better health outcomes due to the increase in scale, granularity, and connectivity of data available. Both countries in scope for Teleport have national-level data holdings of complementary scale, and research infrastructure which is of equivalent maturity to be able to deploy, test, and develop the proposed access solution, which is where Teleport is at its strongest in terms of connecting environments to facilitate multi-TRE analyses.

DARE UK is coordinating “the design and delivery of a coordinated and trustworthy national data research infrastructure to support cross-domain research for public good”. This aim ultimately means funding projects to produce technical developments which will enable existing data providers, TREs, and other technical platforms to be integrated and interoperable, providing efficiencies for researchers to access data and run studies to produce scientific outputs which have meaningful public benefit. Teleport supports this model by providing a technical solution which attempts to introduce as few changes as possible to existing operating frameworks for TREs, frameworks which have become trustworthy over many years of fine tuning, development, and public

engagement. Researchers ultimately need federated analytics solutions which can be accessed and used as seamlessly as possible, and with a relatively low learning curve in terms of their operation so as to appeal to a wide variety of research skill sets. Teleport is attempting to do this by focusing on back-end technical solutions which deal with networking, software deployment, data governance, and security, without any of these burdens falling onto the researcher, who subject to governance approvals should be able to access data from multiple TREs using software sets they are familiar with (perhaps with small amounts of learning involved for certain processes).

Teleport is also complementary to other DARE UK projects which are aiding in the development of the national data infrastructure, particularly in how it could slot into projects such as TRE-FX which is designing another federated analytics solution, SACRO which is providing a framework for the semi-automation of output checking, and SATRE in terms of evaluating how Teleport (or at least the contributing TREs to Teleport) can be evaluated in terms of their compliance with a national standard for TRE architecture.

Public involvement and engagement is integral in ensuring that the proposed solution actually delivers public benefit and impacts patients and the public positively. Whilst Teleport is providing an initial pilot solution, ensuring that the public are broadly comfortable with the approach of working across multiple TREs, data essentially connecting across nations/providers as a result, and that the solution can actually enhance research and outputs feeding back into direct care and societal change, are of key importance from the Teleport perspective.

2. Aim

Teleport's aim with public involvement and engagement is to ensure that the solution we have built delivers science in the public interest. Ultimately, whilst technical solutions are important in enhancing TRE, data provider, and researcher's experiences of hosting, sharing, and using data, they are not successful unless they deliver direct benefits to the public whose data is being analysed through such frameworks.

By consulting with public panels and representatives, our aim is to ensure that there is buy-in to our initial designs, the proposed solution and initial build is seen to be an appropriate use of public funding and will enhance outputs put into the public domain, and that the public believe that what we are constructing has meaningful benefit for them in making things easier for researchers to gain insight into any disease which manifests itself across the UK population (and indeed the world). We envisage that production deployments of Teleport moving forwards after the pilot, where there will be further tangible use cases will benefit from further co-production and consultation with public groups, particularly around the research questions making use of the technical frameworks.

3. Approach

Our PIE strategy for Teleport was based around involving existing public panels and lay members who understood the way that the TREs in scope for Teleport already operated, due to the highly technical nature of the project. We needed to ascertain that the project was going to be designed and delivered in a way which would be publicly acceptable, particularly to those who represent the public whose data is being used and managed through the TREs who were part of the project (SAIL and the Scottish National Safe Haven).

We did not have a direct funding envelope for a large amount of PIE on the project, and therefore had to leverage existing staff, public groups, and coordination to enable us to develop the project with meaningful PIE.

Our initial strategy was conceived alongside PIE coordinators based at SAIL and Public Health Scotland, and scoping of available panels and resources permitted us to coordinate the production of initial documentation prior to consultation with the relevant groups for feedback, opinion, and discussion.

We also wanted to ensure that the public were involved in the project boards and meetings in as far as it was not our teams based in Swansea and Edinburgh developing in isolation, despite the highly technical nature of the project particularly in the early phases, so the recruitment of a lay lead for the project who was able to attend our virtual and in-person meetings was undertaken, who provided public opinion on our direction of travel, and also contributed to the public interface with the panels we presented to throughout the project.

We recognise that in order to gain true and wider public opinion, we need to reach out to wider groups, in the form of surveys, wider presentations and information dissemination, particularly as tangible research projects and outputs are delivered using the Teleport solution for which we can articulate the benefits, enhancements, and impact that Teleport is bringing to the research landscape.

As aforementioned, due to the nature of the project in terms of developing solutions within existing TREs, we decided to make use of panels and public forums who already work with these entities to provide public feedback and scrutiny of our designs and plans which had direct relevance to where they were being developed.

We initially commissioned and wrote a briefing document (DARE UK Teleport Description and Governance Briefing) which could be shared to the coordinators who interface with the relative panels, who in turn then shared this to them as a pre-engagement activity. Once that had been shared, we asked for initial feedback from our PIE coordinators and from the panels themselves, and then engaged with them in presenting the project and asking for their opinions, feelings, and thoughts on the proposal, which was done in parallel to the technical development stages of the project between April and June.

Once our lay lead joined the project (May), we also asked them to interpret the briefing document from a purely lay perspective, and write an advocacy piece which was then disseminated to the SAIL consumer panel to attempt to describe the benefits of our solution and how it fit into the context of ongoing health data research in the UK. Public Health Scotland (Carole Morris) led consultation and engagement with the members of the Public Benefit and Privacy Panel for Health and Social Care (HSC-PBPP), which contains lay members, and presented the project to them in face to face meetings and through the document outlined above (supplied to DARE as part of the project outputs). Swansea University (Chris Orton and Claire Newman) led the same consultation and engagement with the SAIL consumer panel, which is an entirely lay panel and also contains members of SAIL's Information Governance Review Panel (IGRP), also through the supply of the documentation and by presenting to them at the June 2023 quarterly meeting. Feedback was provided directly in the meetings, and also in a follow-up response from the SAIL consumer panel outlining their thoughts on our suggestions, progress, and were particularly keen on hearing from us again once the project had developed further and as we progress into DARE Phase 2, how the solution had been scaled, used by wider research teams, and therefore generating impactful, publicly beneficial outputs.

Presenting at research specific fora, such as the Health Data Research UK Inflammation and Immunity Driver Programme, has also provided wider context to domain-specific view.

We have also made use of the workshops and showcases set up by DARE UK to ensure that other public members who are working on other DARE projects understand the Teleport plans, how it will integrate with other emerging solutions created by DARE pilot projects, and that they believe we are continuing our mission in the public interest, for which there has been agreement.

The project did not want to make any event or consultation prescriptive in terms of training the audience for specific feedback, as we wanted genuine reaction and opinion on whether our proposals were generating public benefit and that they were acceptable within the security, safety, and best practice in health research that the panels have come to expect. In fact, Teleport is only successful if it is able to slot into existing public trust and support for the TREs and data providers who will liaise with it, and so that was our biggest message. The overall atmosphere in collaborating with public groups was therefore entirely inclusive. As we partnered with existing groups through the SAIL consumer panel and HSC-PBPP, coordination of the public interaction was undertaken by the PIE leads for those groups, who ensured that the panel are empowered to feed back as freely as they wish, and by running these meetings virtually, we were able to gain full attendance from those who are members of these groups. The presentation element of the engagements were open to question and answers sessions directly

following, and these fostered open conversation with members of the public with various backgrounds as to how they perceived our plans, how they fit in with current practices, and whether they were going to be seen as positive developments in health science.

Our PIE was primarily undertaken and coordinated by the representatives of institutions involved in the project who maintain the relationship with the panels, and so direct promotion of the project through our briefing document was coordinated by Claire Newman at Swansea University and Carole Morris at Public Health Scotland for the SAIL consumer panel and HSC-PBPP respectively.

We are cognisant of the fact that Wales and Scotland are two constituent countries of the UK which are not as ethnically diverse as, for example, England. Therefore, the primary demography of the panels we engaged are white UK-residents, however on both the SAIL consumer panel and HSC-PBPP there is BAME representation, and recruitment of these members has been entirely due to outreach of these groups rather than being targeted. With the predominant residents of both Wales and Scotland being of white background, it is expectable that panels representing these nations will also be demographically similar. For future endeavours as the Teleport solution is rolled out to other sites, and we spread the word as to our outputs and findings through the project reporting and further consultation, we will be able to gain more representative feedback from across the UK.

Initially, the team who compiled the briefing documentation were the more non-technical members of the project (project management and those who routinely present and work with public audiences) to ensure that we were already translating what is an entirely technical project. All elements of the project were of course reviewed by technical staff to ensure our lay descriptions were correct, and we also disseminated documentation to wider governance and lay stakeholders across Swansea University, University of Edinburgh, and Public Health Scotland to ensure messages were interpretable and not overly technical in nature.

We realised that we did not need to be describing in-depth technical components and mechanisms given we were developing solutions within existing frameworks, but the major element of reporting and sharing information was as to how the landscape currently operates, why there is a need for change, and how scientifically and in the public good, Teleport was introducing change to current systems in a measured, appropriate, and necessary method. Documents were reviewed by those who manage the relationships with public groups within SAIL and Research Data Scotland before dissemination, and post-share, were developed in partnership with our lay lead to distil key messages for ongoing communication.

Due to the pilot nature of the project, the mid-milestone showcase, blog, final showcase, and end of project report are the only dissemination examples we have at present that have been put in the public domain, in addition to the direct engagement and documentation described above. The nature of Teleport is that we have approached the solution development iteratively, with the initial few months being design and testing, and as we enter the latter period of the project, deploying the solution and finessing it to a point where it could be used more broadly by various TRES (not just those within the project). We are hopeful therefore that as the pilot project closes, we will be able to ramp up public engagement through our wider network at SAIL, EPCC, PHS, HDR UK, and beyond to ensure scale-up, tangible use of the systems, and scientific outputs making use of Teleport are disseminated to the public, and Teleport's development is co-produced with public input.

4. Activities and Timelines

April 2023 – initial documentation and lay summaries of the project

April 2023 – draft description and governance briefing document

May 2023 – dissemination of description and governance and briefing document to SAIL consumer panel and HSC-PBPP

May 2023 – Lay lead joined project

May 2023 – Presentation and discussion with HSC-PBPP

June 2023 – Progress and description presentation given to DARE mid-milestone showcase

June 2023 – Presentation and discussion with SAIL consumer panel

July 2023 – Engagement with the DARE UK persona generation workshop, including public perceptions of the wider programme and federation developments

August 2023 – DARE PIE blog shared providing feedback from the above meetings and ongoing developments

September 2023 – Presentation and discussion of the Teleport solution with the HDR UK Inflammation and Immunity Driver Programme (including programme lay leads)

October 2023 – Presentation and discussion at the DARE final milestone showcase

5. Monitoring and Evaluation

We benchmarked our PIE activity based on when information needed to be disseminated to public audiences and when we needed feedback to build into the design, development, and deployment processes.

The largest element of PIE within such a technical project is that the vision, plans, and end product of the solution will deliver what the public believe will benefit them, inspires trust and respectability, and is perceived to not be frivolous in introducing change for the sake of change.

We were able to collect documented feedback from the panel sessions we ran and attended, particularly from the SAIL consumer panel who fed back detailed information including individual comments on the presentation, project plans, progress, and their suggestions for developments. The overarching message was that there was overwhelming support for any technical solution which could permit enhanced data access for researchers looking to undertake science in the public good, but that it would be best received by the public and teams who administer public data hosting services if we could indeed limit the amount of mandatory changes to processes, policies, and operation which is already trusted and known by the public (in the cases of SAIL and eDRIS in the project sense, but more broadly when we approach new partners to take on the Teleport solution over time). Participation and engagement from the panels we approached was exactly how we had envisaged, with open conversation and direct feedback which was provided both through meetings (virtual and face to face) and also in written format so as to summarise group sentiment. We were able to access stakeholders who have knowledge of the systems we were developing and therefore had direct interest in how we were undertaking developments, and as a result, be satisfied that we were indeed developing a worthwhile solution in a way which was being perceived as positive by public members.

As a pilot project which was focused on deploying an initial technical solution between TREs and therefore has much more back-end development, the larger impact of the public feedback will only be felt once the project is rolled out for tangible use cases, both between SAIL and Public Health Scotland, but also with any systems which can produce outputs we can report back to the public, which will in turn validate their feedback, provide testimony as to how we have incorporated their views, and how they perceive we should develop the systems moving forwards. However, it is invaluable that we were able to gather such important insight, validation, and support from public representatives.

6. Reflections and Lessons Learned

As has been mentioned previously, PIE in an extremely technical project is by nature difficult, due to the fact that technical development undertaken by specialists is often not the purpose of undertaking PIE. However, we have been able to engage with relevant public groups to ensure that we translate technical development into real-world impact and describe our plans, designs, and deployments to gauge whether these are correctly shaped and worthwhile. We believe we have had validation from our immediate public panels that the Teleport solution will not present overt governance and ethical issues in connecting TREs in its proposed manner (indeed it supports

existing frameworks with no compromise needed), and that the goal of creating a network of federated research environments is only a positive step forward in terms of making researchers' lives better and translating that enhancement to routine, high quality research which creates direct benefit to the public in many domains, not just health (even though health is our immediate area of contact via the TREs we are starting with). Because the TREs and organisations we have partnered with have such successful PIE through existing groups, we made sure to make use of that mature PIE to ensure we could disseminate information to already-recruited panels and discuss the developments of existing organisations' setups in more detail.

The challenge which this project presented really stems from the translation activity necessary from purely technical developments (as described in the main report) into public benefit and with rational public narrative. We have worked hard to ensure that our messaging always relates back to the end goal of providing publicly beneficial research through our technical solutions, however given the teams who undertake the actual research and who in turn provide tangible public benefit are somewhat removed from this project in terms of direct involvement, a lot of the information dissemination is largely aspirational, which is why we wish to re-engage with the same groups and indeed wider public fora into 2024 and beyond as actual use cases arrive making use of the Teleport solution.

With any future development of this solution, and others funded by DARE UK, it will be crucial to move away from project-specific and relatively siloed PIE, to bringing in programme-led PIE where projects can work more closely together to create unified messages and use a unified forum to disseminate information (thus creating consensus and standardised feedback). Because of the nature of the pilot projects, each project has undertaken PIE in its own style and typically with groups who they are familiar with, but integrating PIE into programme activities, much in the way that we are all integrating into the federated architecture blueprint from a technical standpoint, would benefit the coherence of PIE across the programme and indeed for each project.

7. Discussion and Recommendations

We are happy with the PIE we have undertaken in terms of verifying and validating that our plans were in the public interest and there is perceived benefits to the work we have done. It has also been incredibly important to empower public groups in terms of them shaping how solutions such as Teleport fit in to organisations, research, and science which they are so passionate about and want to provide checks and balances on to ensure that the cyclical nature of research funding, development, and delivery is meaningful and benefits those who need the outputs the most – patients and the wider public.

We realise that through the PIE we have undertaken, the path we have taken in attempting to network TREs that introduces as little change as possible with the burden more on technical teams than governance, ethics, or research teams is a correct direction, and that the public representatives are incredibly supportive of any initiative which seeks to enable pan-UK research to be undertaken more efficiently, because it should only lead to enhanced scientific output quality and therefore improve patient care, scientific understanding, and public awareness of epidemiology.

We are cognisant of the fact that we need to engage much more widely to be able to definitively say that PIE has been achieved at UK-scale and that we have consulted a wide array of public groups and representatives, although due to the time, scope, and budget constraints of the pilot project we feel we have achieved an appropriate start, and are committed to scaling PIE to UK-level with other groups who are not as closely placed as the SAIL and PHS panels to ensure we have wider input into the continual development and rollout of Teleport, as it moves to achieve pan-UK connectivity for research.

As mentioned in the reflections and lessons learned section, a recommendation would be that DARE UK as the commissioner of the work and activities throughout this phase (and previous phases) work more closely with

projects on PIE and perhaps provide a centralised function or wider network of PIE which projects can utilise, collaborate with and across, and therefore ensure that public messaging, dissemination, and development is as united as possible from the outset, rather than create natural siloes of PIE which occurs with no platform to integrate at a higher level. Such a function could also then provide support to projects in commissioning combined documentation and other dissemination options in translating heavily technical or specialist projects to formats which are better received by the public, creating clear and coherent public messages about the emerging technical blueprint of UK data federation, and how this liaises with other national institute delivery which are less technical and generally have more direct scientific or societal topics.